

Production, Purification and Assay of Pectinase Enzyme from Orange Peels

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Abstract:

Production of microbial enzymes at the industrial scale and their commercialization has gained a lot of focus and importance. Use of Microbes as bioreactors was also started due to these developments. Some of the industrially important enzymes from microbial origin include and Pectinases. The organisms were isolated from the fruit peel and were cultured on to Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) agar Plate. The organisms were screened to produce the Pectinase enzyme using Pectin agar media. Microscopic identification and Morphology study revealed that the Fungi isolated was *Aspergillus niger*. The enzyme thus produced was purified by several steps including Salt precipitation. The purified product was used for the Enzyme assay which showed that the activity of the enzyme produced was 0.043 μmol/min/mg. Quantitative estimation of the enzyme was performed by Lowry's Method which showed the concentration of the enzyme to be 24 μg/ml.

The results thus obtained can conclude that the use of *Aspergillus niger* in the industrial production of Pectinase is highly beneficial.

Keywords: Pectinase, Orange peel extract (OPE), *Aspergillus niger*, Enzyme assay.

Introduction:

The Pectinases are the enzymes that can hydrolyse the Pectin polysaccharide into smaller fragments. All the peels of the fruits are made of pectin layer which can be easily digested by the microbial pectinases to extract the juices of the fruits. Therefore, pectinase enzymes are commonly used in processes involving the degradation of plant materials, such as speeding up the extraction of fruit juice [1].

At present, almost all the pectinolytic enzymes used for industrial applications are produced by the fungi, namely *Aspergillus sp.*, *Rhizopus stolonifer*, *Alternaria mali*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Neurospora crassa*,

Penicillium italicum- ACIM F152, and many others. Orange peels are used as substrate for the growth of *Aspergillus niger*. The high cost used in the importation of industrial extracellular enzymes has led to the high cost of finished industrial products. Besides, orange peels cause waste disposal problems since they are being thrown around indiscriminately. This study is therefore aimed at the production of pectinase from *A. niger*, purifying enzyme and assaying the enzyme activity [2].

Pectin or other pectic substances are heterogeneous group of high molecular weight polysaccharides with galacturonic acid residues linked by (1-4) linkages [1]. Pectin's constituting

middle lamella found between the primary cell walls of adjacent young plant cells [2]. There are four main types of pectic substances protopectin, pectic acid, pectinic acid and pectin. Pectin's are the soluble polymeric materials containing pectinic acids as the major component. They can form insoluble protopectin with other structural polysaccharides and proteins located in the cell wall. There are basically three types of pectic enzymes: de-esterifying enzymes (pectinesterases), depolymerizing enzymes (hydrolases and lyases), and protopectinases. They can be further classified as: endo-liquefying or depolymerizing enzymes or exo-saccharifying enzymes [1]. Pectic enzymes contribute to the degradation of pectin by various mechanisms. Elimination of pectic substances is an essential step in many foods processing and wine industries. These enzymes are mainly synthesized by plants and microorganisms [3]. Fungi synthesize polygalacturonases, polymethyl galacturonases, pectin lyases and pectin esterases. The biotechnological potential of pectinolytic enzymes from microorganisms has drawn a great deal of attention for use as biocatalysts in a variety of industrial processes [4]. Compared to non-enzymatic chemical catalysts, biocatalysts (enzymes or whole- cell microorganisms) are known to present some interesting and advantageous features: high efficiency, mild environmentally friendly operation conditions, versatility and high selectivity (chemo-, region- and stereo-selectivity) [5]. The low-cost substrates are used to reduce production costs to produce industrial enzymes [6]. For the industrial production of pectinolytic enzymes, it is important to improve the fermentation conditions for the better production of extracellular enzymes on inexpensive carbon sources such as apple pomace, citric peels, and other agricultural wastes which contain appreciable quantities of pectin [7]

and are degradable by lyases and hydrolases of pectinases [8]. Pectinases have extensive commercial importance for various industrial food applications like in fruit juice industries in order to improve fruit juice yield and clarity. The use of liquefying enzymes for mash treatment results in improvement of juice flow, as maceration of tea leaves [9], processing of cotton fabric [10], leading to a shorter press-time, without the necessity for pressing aids. At the same time pectin is broken down into such an extent that the viscosity of mash is reduced as viscosity relates to molecular weight [11-13]. Pectinases are produced during the natural ripening process of some fruit and act in combination with cellulase. Many microbial strains have been studied to produce pectinase [14]. The main sources for the pectinolytic complex enzymes are yeast, bacteria and many filamentous fungi of which the most relevant ones are *Aspergillus* sp. The pectinase production in yeast has received less attention due to less yield obtained in comparison to bacteria [15]. A range of bacterial and fungal strains produce a variety of pectinolytic enzymes [16, 17]. The selection of high yield pectinase producing strain is difficult, however studies revealed that bacterial strains usually have been shown to produce more yield of pectinolytic enzymes than those of fungal ones [18]. The objectives of the present study were the screening, isolation and identification of pectinase producing bacterial strains from rotten citrus fruit samples (oranges) and determination of their pectinolytic activity [19].

Materials and Methods:

1. Isolation of Pectinolytic Fungi from Orange Peels:

Orange peels (~1 kg) have been collected and the peels were kept under moist condition for

few days in the air tight condition. Once the rotting of the peels began, the growth of the fungi started. This was used as the inoculums for the isolation of the organisms from the peel.[20]

2. Media Preparation Phase:

Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA), Czapek Dextrose broth (CDB), Potato Dextrose broth (PDB) was prepared as mentioned Deepanwita Deka et al., 2018 [21] and further utilised specifically for the growth of dermatophytes and other types of fungi.

3. Screening for the Pectinase Enzyme Production:

Phosphate buffer is used for the selective growth of these pectin-releasing microorganisms. Prepared according to the following composition of agar plate to screen the pectinase enzymes production.. Briefly, 0.2 gm KH_2PO_4 , 0.3 gm K_2HPO_4 , 0.01gm MgSO_4 and 2.5 gm agar were added in to 100 ml of distilled water. After the media prepared and sterilized, agar plate was prepared. Microbial culture was spread out on the agar plate by simple streak plate technique. The plate is stored in an inverted manner at room temperature for microbial growth. After incubation, the plates were screened to identify hydrolysed areas, indicating a positive result from pectinase production. In addition, the obtained colonies were observed under a microscope. [22].

4. Pectinase enzyme production by liquid state fermentation:

Aspergillus niger inoculum was inoculated in a basal medium for the production of pectinase, which consisted of 0.2 gm KH_2PO_4 , 0.3 gm K_2HPO_4 , 0.01 gm MgSO_4 and 1 g of pectin in 100 ml of distilled water. The media pH 4.5 was set and sterilized media with autoclave at 121°C for 15 min. Media was Incubated by using submerged liquid fermentation at 25°C for 10 to 12 days. [22].

5. Crude Enzyme Extraction by Filtration:

The crude enzymes were separate from mycelia mat by using spore bodies filtration technique. The broth was filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and then centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 15 minutes. Crude enzymes extract supernatant was used for measuring the pectinase activity.

6. Partial purification of enzyme by Ammonium sulfate precipitation and dialysis:

Ammonium sulfate precipitation was used for the partial purification of the crude enzymes. 44 gm of ammonium sulfate was added in to 100 ml suspension of crude enzymes and Pinch-by-pinch ammonium sulphate was used complete saturation of the enzymes under cold condition. Further purification was done by using dialysis (ref. for dialysis). [23].

7. Enzyme assay using pectin and its estimation by lowry method:

Pectinesterase activity was measured by increase in free carboxyl group by titrating against NaOH in the present of a Phenolphthalein (PH indicator). Briefly, 20 ml of 1% pectin was dissolved in 0.5M NaCl (pH -7) with 4 ml of crude enzyme extract was incubated for 1 hour. After incubation, the solution was titrated against 1 N NaOH to reach PH 7 using Phenolphthalein as indicator. Colour change was observed from colourless to pink.

$$\text{Pectin esterase activity} = \frac{V_s - V_b}{V} \times 100 \times \frac{1}{t} \times 50$$

Where, V_s - Volume of NaOH used to titer sample (ml), V_b - Volume of NaOH used to titer blank (ml), V - Volume of incubation mixture (ml), t - Reaction time (min).

Pectin esterase activity was expressed as milli equivalents of NaOH consumed min^{-1} per ml^{-1} of crude enzyme extract [24]. The protein concentration was measured by Lowry's Method [25].

8. Enzyme Immobilization:

The enzymes was immonilized by using sodium aliinate beads. 0.3 gm of sodium alginate was dissolved in 10 ml distilled water and mixed well. 3 ml purified enzymes was added into the sodium alginate. The pectinase-alginate mixture was dropped in the rythmic mannor into 2 % calcium chloride solution by using a syringe. Pectinase-alginate mixture was polymerized into the calcium chloride solution and bead was fromed. [26].

Results and Discussion:

1. Isolation, Screening and identification of the Fungi:

Isolation of *Aspergillus niger* from orange peel was represented in Figure (1). Fungi colonies was collected from the fruit peels and growth on the Sabouraud Dextrose agar (SDA) agar plate, Czapek Dextrose broth, and Potato

Dextrose broth (figure 2). The pectinase producing fungi was grown on the SDA media, because SDA media contains pectin as main substrate which support the selectively growth to pectinase producing fungi. Light green and black colonies were observed after 10th day of inoculation. The cells were densely populated and filamentous growth was seen after 15 days of inoculation. The mycelia were stained with lacto phenol cotton blue and observed under 40X magnification (figure 3 A and B). Based on the colony morphology the Mycelia were identified as *Aspergillus niger* [29]. The culture was further used for production the enzyme using PSAM medium. All morphological contrasting colonies were isolated by repeated streaking and sub culturing. Genus was identified by relating the microscopic features of the cultures to “Atlas of Mycology” by Barnett and Hunter (1972) [30].

Figure (1): Fungus isolation, [A] storage of orange peels in Ziplock bag, [B] initiates the growth of fungi, [C] obtained rotten peels as a source of fungi.

Figure (2): Fungus growth obtained by employing, [A] Sabouraud Dextrose agar, [B] Czapek Dextrose broth, [C] Potato Dextrose broth.

Figure (3): Fungus growth, [A] Sabouraud Dextrose agar, [B] microscopically mycelium was identified as *Aspergillus niger*.

3. Pectinase enzyme production by liquid state fermentation and its partial purification:

The culture of previous step was further used to produce the enzyme using PSAM medium. The culture was incubated for 20 days for the complete production of the extracellular enzyme. The enzyme thus produced was purified by several techniques like Filtration,

Centrifugation, Salt precipitation dialysis and immobilization as shown in figure (4). The purified product was used for the Enzyme assay which showed that the activity of the enzyme produced was **0.043 μ mol/min/mg**. Quantitative estimation of the enzyme was performed by Lowry's Method which showed the concentration of the enzyme to be **24 μ g/ml**.

Figure (4): Partial purification steps of an enzyme includes; [A] Pectinase enzyme production, [B] Crude enzyme extraction by filtration, [C] Ammonium sulfate precipitation, [D] Dialysis [E] partial pure enzyme solution and [F] Enzyme immobilization.

Conclusion:

This investigation recommends that orange peel could be an alluring and promising substrate to deliver pectinases by *Aspergillus niger*. The crude enzyme was further purified by using Salt precipitation dialysis. The purified product was used for the Enzyme assay which showed that the activity of the enzyme produced was 0.043 μ mol/min/mg. Quantitative estimation of the enzyme was performed which showed the concentration of the enzyme to be 24 μ g/ml. In addition, this work will go as a promising data to scientists who need to investigate the potential outcomes of changing over waste to riches and value addition. Since orange peels used in this cycle are promptly open as waste with practically zero cost and furthermore contain an obvious measure of pectin, they can be viewed as an ease substrate for proficient and conservative creation of pectinases utilizing Fungi. Immobilized enzyme further can be used in food industry.

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